

Style for IRRN Contributors

Units of measure and styles vary from country to country. To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style guidelines:

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).

- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).

- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.

- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.

- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.

- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.

- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.

- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.

- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

- Type all contributions double-spaced. ■

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Karnataka male-sterile rice—KMS1

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A male-sterile rice plant isolated at Mandya, Karnataka, India, in 1972 was multiplied clonally at IRRI in February 1979. We designated it KMS1 (for Karnataka male-sterile). In greenhouse and field observations, female fertility appeared normal; seed-setting was 90% by hand pollination and 4–42% through natural cross-pollination. As in previous observations in India, there was no seed-set when the panicles were covered. But unlike in India, a few (1–2%) stainable pollen grains were observed under the microscope, although meiosis in those grains appeared normal. The new environment may possibly have induced this difference. As has been reported in barley, the pressure exerted by a few stainable pollen grains may not be adequate for the anthers to dehisce and shed pollen; thus, seed-setting failed when the panicles were covered.

Data gathered from 53 stubbles planted among 32 tall and 23 semidwarf

rices in the IRRI observational yield trial and hybridization block in the 1979 dry and wet seasons showed that natural cross-pollination can produce 4 to 24% seed-set. Seed-setting was higher in the dry season (17–42%) than in the wet (4–37%).

KMS1 ratoons vigorously like its male parent, C435, and is relatively free from virus attack, although it has been maintained clonally since 1972.

When KMS1 was backcrossed to its female parent IR8, the 64 progenies were fertile to varying degrees. When backcrossed to the male parent the three progenies tended to be sterile. Because the number of backcross progeny for the latter was small, we again backcrossed the male parent. The progenies (IR30638) are being grown for observation in the 1980 dry-season F₁ nursery. IR30638 was also crossed with the monogenic recessive male-sterile IR36. The F₁s (IR30431) are being planted in the 1980 dry-season nursery.

Since 1973, KMS1 has been widely used in hybridization work in Karnataka. IRRI is investigating the mechanism responsible for male sterility. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease Resistance

Varietal reaction of rice cultivars to *Pyricularia oryzae* in Argentina

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In December 1978, 197 rice experimental lines and traditional varieties were artificially inoculated in the field. The nursery plot design, the soil fertilization, and the seeding methods were based on the techniques suggested by S.H. Ou of IRRI.

Because of a lack of natural field infection, the seedlings were sprayed at the fourth-leaf stage with a *P. oryzae* conidial suspension that had been prepared with strain cultures of the pathogen V3-78-1, V3-78-2, CU3-78, G4-78, LP5-78, and SF4-78. Such strains were isolated from infected material sent from various places in the provinces of Entre Rios, Buenos Aires (La Plata), and Santa Fe of Argentina.

The misato agar and barley seeds sterilized in misato solution were used as sporulating media. The suspension was adjusted to conidial concentration at